

A Unique Fixed Point Result on C-G-MS

K.Prudhvi*

Department of Mathematics, University College of Science, Saifabad,
Osmania University, Hyderabad, Telangana, India.

Received: 08 Jul 2025

Accepted: 19 Jul 2025

Published Online: 31 Aug 2025

Abstract: In this paper, we establish a fixed point theorem in C-G-MS(Complete- Generalized -Metric Space), which is a generalization and extension of some of the well known comparable results existing in the literature.

Key words: Contractive mapping, fixed point, G-MS(Generalized Metric Space), convergent sequence.

AMS Mathematics Subject Classification(2010):74H10, 54H25.

1. Introduction

Banach contraction mapping principle is most important and it plays vital role in nonlinear analysis. In 1968 Kannan [3] established fixed point theorem which is also most important result in fixed point theory, from then onwards so many applications and generalizations were came in this field. (see for e.g. 1-13) .In 1977 Rhoades [7] analyzed the different types of contractive conditions. In 2000, Branciari [2] introduced generalized metric spaces by replacing triangle inequality by similar ones which involve four or more points instead of three and improved Banach contraction principle. And recently Azam and Arshad [1] obtained results on Kannan fixed point theorem on generalized metric space. In the present paper, we prove a fixed point result on Banach-Kannan fixed point theorem in C-M-GS. Our result is a generalization and an extension of the results of [1].

1.1. Preliminaries

For our main results we need some of the following definitions which are due to [1].

Definition 1.1. Let X be a non empty set .Suppose that the mapping $\rho : X \times X \longrightarrow N$ satisfies the following:

- (1) $0 \leq \rho(\alpha, \beta)$ for all $\alpha, \beta \in X$ and $\rho(\alpha, \beta) = 0$ if and only if $\alpha = \beta$;
- (2) $\rho(\alpha, \beta) = \rho(\beta, \alpha)$ for all $\alpha, \beta \in X$;
- (3) $\rho(\alpha, \beta) \leq \rho(\alpha, \xi) + \rho(\xi, \gamma) + \rho(\gamma, \beta)$ for all $\alpha, \beta \in X$ and for all distinct points $\gamma, \xi \in X \setminus \{\alpha, \beta\}$.

Then ρ is called a G-M(Generalized Metric) and (X, ρ) is a G-M-S(Generalized Metric Space).

Definition 1.2. Let $\{X_n\}$ be a a sequence in X and $x \in X$.If for every $\epsilon > 0$ there is an $n_0 \in N$ such that $\rho(x_n, x) < \epsilon$ for all $n > n_0$, then x_n is said to be convergence , x_n convergences to x and x is the limit point of x_n . We denote this by $\lim_{n \rightarrow \infty} x_n = x$, or $x_n \longrightarrow x$, as $n \longrightarrow \infty$.

Definition 1.3. Let $\{X_n\}$ be a a sequence in X and $x \in X$.If for every $\epsilon > 0$ there is an $n_0 \in N$ such that $\rho(x_n, x) < \epsilon$ for all $n > n_0$, then x_n is called Cauchy sequence in X.

Definition 1.4. Every Cauchy sequence is convergent in X , then X is called a complete generalized metric space.

Remark 1.1. [1] (i) $\rho(a_n, y) \rightarrow \rho(a, y)$ and $\rho(x, a_n) \rightarrow \rho(x, a)$ whenever a_n is a sequence in X with $a_n \rightarrow a \in X$.

(ii) X becomes a Hausdorff topological space with neighborhood basis given by : $B = B(x, r) : x \in X, r \in (0, \infty)$, where $B(x, r) = \{y \in X : \rho(x, y) < r\}$.

2. Main Results

Now we obtain our main theorem.

Theorem 2.1. Let (X, ρ) be a C-G-MS (Complete-Generalized -Metric Space) and let the mapping $A : X \rightarrow X$ satisfies the following:

$$\rho(Ax, Ay) \leq \lambda_1\rho(x, y) + \lambda_2\rho(x, Ax) + \lambda_3\rho(y, Ay) + \lambda_4\rho(x, Ay) + \lambda_5\rho(Ax, y). \quad (1)$$

For all $x, y \in X$, $\lambda_1, \lambda_2, \lambda_3, \lambda_4, \lambda_5 \geq 0$ and $\lambda_1 + \lambda_2 + \lambda_3 + 2\lambda_4 + \lambda_5 < 1$. Then A has a unique fixed point.

Proof. Let $x_0 \in X$ be any arbitrary point in X . Let $x_1 = A(x_0)$. If $x_1 = x_0$ then $x_0 = A(x_0)$ this means that x_0 is a fixed point of A and there is nothing to prove. Assume that $x_1 \neq x_0$, let $x_2 = A(x_1)$. In this way we can define a sequence of points in X as follows

$$\begin{aligned} x_{n+1} &= Ax_n = A^{n+1}x_0, \quad n = 0, 1, 2, 3 \dots \text{ Using by (1) we get that} \\ \rho(x_n, x_{n+1}) &= \rho(Ax_{n-1}, Ax_n), \\ &\leq \lambda_1\rho(x_{n-1}, x_n) + \lambda_2\rho(x_{n-1}, Ax_{n-1}) + \lambda_3\rho(x_n, Ax_n) + \lambda_4\rho(x_{n-1}, Ax_{n-1}) + \lambda_5\rho(Ax_{n-1}, x_n), \\ &\leq \lambda_1\rho(x_{n-1}, x_n) + \lambda_2\rho(x_{n-1}, x_n) + \lambda_3\rho(x_n, x_{n+1}) + \lambda_4\rho(x_{n-1}, x_{n+1}) + \lambda_5\rho(x_n, x_n), \\ &\leq (\lambda_1 + \lambda_2 + \lambda_4)\rho(x_{n-1}, x_n) + (\lambda_3 + \lambda_4)\rho(x_n, x_{n+1}), \\ &\leq \frac{(\lambda_1 + \lambda_2 + \lambda_4)}{(1 - (\lambda_3 + \lambda_4))}\rho(x_{n-1}, x_n), \\ &\leq \alpha\rho(x_{n-1}, x_n), \text{ where } \alpha = \frac{(\lambda_1 + \lambda_2 + \lambda_4)}{(1 - (\lambda_3 + \lambda_4))} < 1. \end{aligned}$$

We can also suppose that x_0 is not a periodic point. In fact if $x_n = x_0$, then

$$\begin{aligned} \rho(x_0, Ax_0) &= \rho(x_n, Ax_n), \\ &= \rho(A^n x_0, A^{n+1} x_0), \\ &\leq \rho(A^{n-1} x_0, A^n x_0), \\ &\leq \alpha^2 \rho(A^{n-2} x_0, A^{n-1} x_0) \leq \dots \leq \alpha^n \rho(x_0, Ax_0), \\ (1 - \alpha^n)\rho(x_0, Ax_0) &\leq 0. \end{aligned}$$

It follows that x_0 is a fixed point of A . Thus in the sequel of point we can suppose that $A^n x_0 \neq x_0$, for $n = 1, 2, 3, \dots$

Now (1) implies that

$$\begin{aligned} \rho(A^n x_0, A^{n+m} x_0) &\leq \lambda_1\rho(A^{n-1} x_0, A^{n+m-1} x_0) + \lambda_2\rho(A^{n-1} x_0, A^n x_0) + \lambda_3\rho(A^{n+m-1-1} x_0, A^{n+m} x_0) + \\ &\lambda_4\rho(A^{n-1} x_0, A^{n+m} x_0) + \lambda_5\rho(A^{n-1} x_0, A^{n+m-1} x_0), \\ &\leq \lambda_1\alpha^{n+m-1}\rho(Ax_0, x_0) + \lambda_2\alpha^{n-1}\rho(x_0, Ax_0) + \lambda_3\alpha^{n+m-1}\rho(x_0, Ax_0) \\ &+ \lambda_4\alpha^{n-1}\rho(x_0, Ax_0) + \lambda_5\alpha^{n+m-1}\rho(Ax_0, x_0), \\ &\rightarrow 0 \text{ as } m, n \rightarrow \infty. \end{aligned}$$

Implies that, $\rho(x_n, x_{n+m}) \rightarrow 0$ as $m, n \rightarrow \infty$.

Therefore, $\{x_n\}$ is a sequence in X . Since X is complete there exists a point $p \in X$ such that $x_n \rightarrow p$. By rectangular property we get that

$$\begin{aligned} \rho(Ap, p) &\leq \rho(Ap, A^n x_0) + \rho(A^n x_0, A^{n+1} x_0) + \rho(A^{n+1} x_0, p), \\ &= \lambda_1 \rho(p, A^{n-1} x_0) + \lambda_2 \rho(p, Ap) + \lambda_3 \rho(A^{n-1} x_0, A^n x_0) + \lambda_4 \rho(p, A^n x_0) + \lambda_5 \rho(Ap, A^{n-1} x_0) + \alpha^n \rho(x_0, Ax_0) + \\ &\rho(A^{n+1} x_0, p), \\ (1-\lambda_2) \rho(Ap, p) &\leq \lambda_1 \rho(p, A^{n-1} x_0) + \lambda_3 \rho(A^{n-1} x_0, A^n x_0) + \lambda_4 \rho(p, A^n x_0) + \lambda_5 \rho(Ap, A^{n-1} x_0) + \alpha^n \rho(x_0, Ax_0) + \\ &\rho(A^{n+1} x_0, p), \\ &\leq \frac{\lambda_1}{(1-\lambda_2)} \rho(p, A^{n-1} x_0) + \frac{\lambda_3}{(1-\lambda_2)} \rho(A^{n-1} x_0, A^n x_0) + \frac{\lambda_4}{(1-\lambda_2)} \rho(p, A^n x_0) + \frac{\lambda_5}{(1-\lambda_2)} \rho(Ap, A^{n-1} x_0) + \frac{\alpha^n}{(1-\lambda_2)} \rho(x_0, Ax_0) + \\ &\frac{1}{(1-\lambda_2)} \rho(A^{n+1} x_0, p). \end{aligned}$$

Letting $n \rightarrow \infty$ we get that, Using the fact that

$\rho(a_n, y) \rightarrow \rho(a, y)$ and $\rho(x, a_n) \rightarrow \rho(x, a)$ whenever a_n is a sequence in X with $a_n \rightarrow a \in X$. We get that $p = Ap$. Therefore A has a fixed point. Now we prove that A has a unique fixed point. Now we assume that there exists another point $q \in X$ such that $q = Aq$.

$$\begin{aligned} \text{Now } \rho(q, p) &= \rho(Aq, Ap), \\ &\leq \lambda_1 \rho(p, q) + \lambda_2 \rho(p, Ap) + \lambda_3 \rho(q, Aq) + \lambda_4 \rho(p, Aq) + \lambda_5 \rho(Ap, q), \\ &\leq \lambda_1 \rho(p, q) + \lambda_2 \rho(p, p) + \lambda_3 \rho(q, q) + \lambda_4 \rho(p, q) + \lambda_5 \rho(p, q), \\ &\leq \lambda_1 \rho(p, q) + \lambda_4 \rho(p, q) + \lambda_5 \rho(p, q), \\ &\leq (\lambda_1 + \lambda_4 + \lambda_5) \rho(p, q), \\ \rho(q, p) &\leq 0. \text{ Implies that } \rho(q, p) = 0, \text{ that is, } p = q. \end{aligned}$$

□

Remark 2.2. If we choose $\lambda_1 = \lambda_4 = \lambda_5 = 0$ and $\lambda_2 = \lambda_3 = \lambda$, then we get the result of [1].

3. Conclusion

In this paper, our results are more general and extension than the results of [1].

Conflict of interest: The author has declared there is no conflict of interest.

Acknowledgment

The author is grateful to the reviewers to review this research article and also give the valuable suggestions to improve this article.

References

- [1] Azam A and Arshad M, Kannan fixed point theorem on generalized metric spaces, The J. Nonlinear .Sci.,2008; 1,no.1,45-48.
- [2] Branciari A, A fixe dpoint theorem of Banach-Caccippoli type on a class of generalized metric spaces, Publ. Math. Debrecen, 2000; 57/1-2, 31-37.
- [3] Kannan R, Some results on fixed points, Bull.Calcutta math.Soc., 1968; 60, 71-76.
- [4] Moradi S, Kannan fixed point theorem on complete metric spaces and on generalized metric spaces depended an another function, arXiv:0903.1577 v1[math;FA], 2009; 9 Mar, 1-6.

- [5] Prudhvi K, Common fixed Point results for generalized contractive conditions in cone metric spaces, American Journal of Mathematics and Statistics,2013; 3(5), 265-267.
- [6] Prudhvi K, A Result on “ Common Fixed Points “for Pair of OWC-Mappings in C- MS, American Journal of Applied Mathematics and Statistics,2023; Vol. 11, No.3, 98-99.
- [7] Prudhvi K, Study on Fixed Points for OWC in Symmetric Spaces, Asia Mathematika,2023; Vol.7, Issue 3, 72- 75.
- [8] Prudhvi K, Common fixed points on occasionally weakly compatible self-mappings in CMS, Asia Mathematika, 2023 ; Vol.7, Issue.2:13-16.
- [9] K.Prudhvi, A Result on “ Common Fixed Points “for Pair of OWC-Mappings in C- MS, American Journal of Applied Mathematics and Statistics,2023; Vol. 11, No.3,98-99.
- [10] Prudhvi K, Results on fixed points for WC-Mappings satisfying generalized contractive condition in C- metric spaces, Asia Mathematika,2024; Vol-8 Issue-1, 112 – 117.
- [11] Prudhvi K, A unique common fixed point result for compatible reciprocal continuous four self - maps in complete metric space, Asia Mathematika,2024; Vol-8 Issue-3, 10–13.
- [12] K.Prudhvi, A Fixed Point Theorem for Expansion onto Mappings on CCM-Spaces, Asia Mathematika, 2025; Vol.5, Issue 2, 21-24.
- [13] K.Prudhvi, Study on Extended B-K Fixed Point Theorem on CGM-Space Depended on an Another Function Asia Mathematika, 2025; Vol.5, Issue 2, 25-28.
- [14] B.E.Rhoades, A comparison of various definitions of contractive mappings, Trans. Amer. Math. Sci.,1977; 26, 257-290.